

EVOLUTION OF SOUND INSULATION ASPECTS AND REQUIREMENTS IN THE HISTORY

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ABSTRACT

The problem of city soundscape has always been topic of a lot of researches and discussions starting in Antiquity (and maybe even earlier) continuing until today. Common problem of all cities were various trades, mills, coppersmiths, etc. As the society started to develop and with all the inventions of modern world, people started to perceive city noise more sensual. Medical researches showed that inadequate noise is dangerous to human ears. Moreover, exposition to high noise levels for longer period of time can cause deafness and also psychological problems. During ages city inhabitants together with municipalities have tried to bring order and regulations into the unregulated spread of various noise sources. With such actions some of modern guidelines and recommendations came into general use. This paper brings brief overview on how people dealt with noise in connection with their living in dwellings.

INTRODUCTION

The problem with noise in residential parts of cities is not new and noise has been recognized for centuries as dangerous to human health [Rosen, 1974]. The oldest regulations dealing with trades in respect to noise date back to ancient Rome. During centuries several regulations and guidelines have appeared, which were always influenced by experience of either city planners or house designers and architects. There is very little information about acoustic and noise in dwellings since the society was more focused on environmental noise in cities and its adverse effect on health. This paper brings several references on how people dealt with noise since past until modern regulations came into general use.

NOISE AWARENESS DATED TO ANCIENT TIMES

The subject of acoustics was probably developed in ancient Greece by Pythagoras around 530 BC. As we have already mentioned the oldest guidelines connected with noise of trades placed in the residential parts of the cities dated into ancient times. One of the rules was a rule which prohibited to establish coppersmiths' trades in streets where already professor lived [Wiethaup, 1966]. Architects of ancient Rome already understood that noise from streets could be disturbing and moreover it could influence health of inhabitants. Their house designs already took into account the phenomenon of environmental noise. As an example, we could look at the ancient Roman domus. It was a dwelling for upper class Roman family. The streets of ancient Rome were

dangerous and noisy, therefore, to prevent dwellers from noise, the windows of domus were only rarely placed on the outer walls. If so, they were few of them and were not very large (Figure 1). The fact that ill people need tranquillity has been known since Antiquity. A famous medical researcher of that times Galen promoted the need of keeping balance between day activity and undisturbed sleep during night to keep people healthy [Burns, 1976].

Figure 1. Ancient Roman domus – very little or none windows in outer wall used as protection against dust, heat and noise from streets

The Roman engineer Vitruvius aimed several chapters of his book to building design of open theatres. He recommended their location away from windy areas to and give some guidelines on placement of entrances. He inspired himself in ancient Greek treatises. Vitruvius developed many recommendations how to build theatre. It led to semi-circular shape and raked seating of such structures. He also discussed the use of sounding vessels (Helmholtz resonators), but he had never used them in building of theatres in Rome, since Roman theatres were built from wood which does not lead to problems with reflections in comparison with stone used in Greek architecture.

TRADES OF MIDDLE AGES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON NOISE POLLUTION

No significant writings on the acoustics of buildings survive from mediaeval or Renaissance times [Hunt, 1992]. From the 12th century on, music started to develop. This development shows evidence that people in those times understood acoustics in cathedrals, however the qualities of buildings for music performances are related more to the experiences and skills of composers and musicians, rather to the designers and architects. Long reverberation times in such buildings influenced also music, since musical rhythms in such environment have to be slow to be intelligible.

Starting at 14th century, there were some actions organized towards allocation of noisy activities – hand workers, flapping mills, etc. – out of the cities. In cases where it was not possible, there was an effort to place them at least in one part of the city, as far from dwelling buildings as possible [Poulussen, 1987]. The noise from the mills was, of course, unpleasant for dwellers. Nowadays, we are not able to imagine the sound of mills could be disturbing. For today's society, mill is picture of quiet rural life. Municipal authorities of cities establish licences for those who wanted to operate the mill.

Book of Vitruvius was published at the end of 15th century and was known by most of architects and designers who tried to follow the recommendations written inside. From that times attention of building designers was focused on speech intelligibility in building interiors [Polio, 1960]. Special attention was paid especially to theatres and debating chambers used by politicians. The understanding of influence of volume

and reflectivity of the surrounding surfaces on speech and music intelligibility led to usage of several pragmatic rules. They were widely using three types of material: (i) stone or plaster to enhance reflections, (ii) curtains and tapestries made from woven fabric to absorb the sound and (iii) timber panels something in between of previous two. Such materials were widely used also in buildings for living to decrease or increase the (un)wanted noise.

LIVING IN INDUSTRIAL SOCIETY

In 19th century the sounds produced by trades were everywhere and influenced everybody. These various sounds led to many local guidelines and restrictions connected with noise. Some local laws included regulation of singing and shouting on Sundays, barking of dogs, street music, whistling in nights and making noise in the neighbourhood of churches, hospitals and other important institutions [Franinovic, 2013]. Most of the time it was about prohibition to make noise in particular days (weekends) in particular hours (nights), in particular places and to make noise without license for trades. Traffic noise from caused by carts started to be also a large problem in cities. In many European towns of 19th century, straw or sand were putting down on the pavement in front of hospitals and homes for sick by inhabitants to reduce the noise from increasing traffic [Bailey, 1996; Cowan, 2006; Schafer 1994; Verslag 1934].

From the end of 19th century, noise was considered to be one of the main factors in developing the research topic household hygiene – noise, light, ventilation and bacteria. Some of guidelines from those times emphasized the dangerous influence of the noise to nervous life of ear and recommended to nervous dwellers to avoid (if possible) loud apartment buildings [Boltenstern, 1904; Esmarch, 1897]. Exactly because of this ears' exposure to urban noise and the nervous dangers it brought, people in dwellings begin calling for means of protection in the form of acoustic soundproofing and acoustic insulation. The ear started to be understood as an exceptionally vulnerable sense organ in comparison with the eye [Lessing, 1908].

Later on, many of European countries had instituted regulations - civil codes against the disturbance of neighbours, which was aimed at indecent sounds, offensive noise and rude behaviour. Some of European countries excluded noise caused by trades and factories from these regulations (Dam, 1888). The civil code assumed that owners of properties close to factories profited from the increases in the price and rents of their property. Therefore, people without property did not have chance to win a case against noise under civil codes [Saul, 1996].

The beginning of 20th century has brought conflicts between neighbours. It was due to emergence of electronic sound reproduction systems (such as gramophone and radio). This has opened questions about sound insulation between dwellings. These cases end up with a discussion in Dutch local politics in 1913 in Rotterdam [Bank, 2000]. Proposal, which would regulate using of “mechanical musical instruments” would be unfairly unfavourable to lower classes since gramophone were “musical instruments” of these classes. It took a lot of time and discussions but at the end the city council accepted the proposed ordinance which regulated noise from gramophones and these regulations started to be controlled by police. After this change, big discussions arose between conservatives and communists [MA, 1914]. The lower working class wanted to listen to the radio during the night, after they came home tired from the work. On the other hand the only acceptable music for upper class was music of classical instruments and they felt disturbed by gramophones playing “modern” music. The problem of noise from gramophones and radios had become very political. After a lot of discussions and fights city council decided to deal with this special case fairly. They started to regulate not only noise from radios and gramophones but also the one from musical instruments [Van Den Bogaert, 2006]. This was a sign that there was not more distinction in assessment of music noise but there was a need to measure noise. Amsterdam police started to collaborate with Dutch acoustician, prof. Cornelis Zwikker from TU Delft, on developing of the device that would measure noise levels. The invention of first sound level meter changed evaluation of noise from subjective to objective [Bijsterveld, 2008].

Another problem in cities was increasing number of cars and increasing traffic noise. The sound of the surrounding world was not same when we compare e.g. 1900 and 1930 (fig. 2). People had to challenge different city soundscape. The change in perception of city noise was part of large reform in urban planning, public health program and trying to put current knowledge from each field into the life of modern 20th century's city.

Figure 2. Collection and classification of city noise sources according to [19]

MODERN ACOUSTICAL STANDARDS

The first standards of modern world which were related to buildings appeared in 19th century. The main aim of these standards was motivated by necessity of society to increase the fire protection of cities and by ensuring structural stability of buildings. There was no mention of acoustics in such standards [Rasmussen, 2010]. Over next decades the requirements for single sound insulation appeared in some local building codes. Nowadays, there exist few standards related to the general acoustic comfort of interior, which are being constantly adjusted and adapted to a modern building material and techniques as well as modern life style [Rasmussen, 2010].

CONCLUSIONS

There is not a lot of information on how people had dealt with noise in their dwellings before standards and regulations on noise and building development came into general use. This paper brought several of such examples when dwellers were disturbed by noise from the outside or neighbour noise. Most of them came up from rather from experience than objective measures or calculations. For the future work it is important to research how homes of people looked like and what kind of materials they used to unconsciously increase room acoustic and building acoustic performance of structures and spaces.

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